

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY CONCEPT IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

Huseynova A.,

Ismayilov U.

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management

Abstract

Due to the constantly evolving competition in the market economy, the importance of applying Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has significantly increased in the latter years. The reason for increased completion is the improvement of new technologies, battle over customers, quality of the product and service which in the meantime forces managers to reconsider the complexity of the business management system. The globally accepted concept of CSR involves businesses contributing for the continuous development of all areas of society. Companies usually go beyond the obligations outlined in legislation within the framework of CSR and take on voluntary commitments.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, philanthropy, environment.

Due to the constantly evolving competition in the market economy, the importance of applying Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has significantly increased in the latter years. The reason for increased completion is the improvement of new technologies, battle over customers, quality of the product and service which in the meantime forces managers to reconsider the complexity of the business management system. CSR needs to operate as the basic principle of management. The company's commitment to corporate social responsibility involves participating in economic, environmental, and social initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable development for both the company and society overall. Every socially responsible corporation should aim to endorse and execute significant social initiatives, guided by sustainable development principles, and engage in activities targeting priority areas.

Corporate social responsibility is a culture of voluntary behavior aimed at preserving and developing society and the environment.

Corporate social responsibility is a concept that supports economic, ecological, cultural, and social development, contributing to making the world livable and sustainable, thereby improving the quality of life for all communities.

Corporate social responsibility makes the corporation accountable for all actions that may affect people, communities, and the environment in any way. This implies that it is important for the company to mitigate any potential harm to people and society that may result from its activities. In CSR, companies combine social and environmental components into their policies and voluntarily engage with stakeholders in mutually effective relationships.

Corporate social responsibility entails the responsibility of the company as an employer, business partner, "citizen," and member of society (the boundaries of society are determined by the geographical scope of the company's activities: region, city, country, global level). It is part of the company's ongoing strategy to enhance its presence in society and develop its business. It represents an opportunity for the company

to have a positive impact on the community in which it operates. CSR involves integrating social, environmental, and other aspects that concern stakeholders into business operations.

Philanthropy or CSR? In many cases, CSR and philanthropy get mixed up in terms of their meaning. However, these are completely different concepts. CSR is a purposeful strategic direction that encompasses the company's action plan. The company's CSR activities, budget, and strategy are predetermined and implemented throughout the year, while philanthropy occurs once or several times a year. CSR involves engaging all employees of the company, whereas philanthropy is typically limited to the activities of the company leadership. CSR plays a fundamental guiding role in encouraging organizations to behave ethically and responsibly towards their stakeholders and the society, helping them to make decisions and implement them in that direction. However, it would be wrong to confuse this activity with sponsorship or philanthropy. The result generated by projects conducted within the framework of CSR helps increase the credibility and value of the product or service in the society. In fact, CSR should already be accepted as a quality criterion for companies. The main indicator of CSR projects is their sustainability. These projects should combine the characteristics that can bring useful, long-term benefits to society and success in the public-social sphere. Moreover, these projects should have a measurable and accountable evaluation process. In that sense, a strategy for execution and implementation, aligned with the objectives, plans, and goals, should be developed, properly planned, and shared with all interested parties willing to collaborate. Any company deciding on CSR projects should prepare an action plan consistent with its strategy accordingly. All of these tasks should be managed with services proposed by professionals. Company leadership should create conditions for this process.

Areas of impact of CSR activities:

- It leads to the humanization of society, thereby creating a favorable environment for businesses.

- It helps establish and maintain a positive image of the institution.
- It assists in regulating relations with influential participants in the market, such as government and municipal authorities.
- It creates an efficient workforce, minimizes employee turnover, and facilitates the attraction of talented employees.
- It contributes to the development of the institution to achieve its goals.

Forms of CSR implementation:

The globally accepted concept of CSR involves businesses contributing for the continuous development of all areas of society. Companies usually go beyond the obligations outlined in legislation within the framework of CSR and take on voluntary commitments. They provide support to the following areas not only for economic but also for the comprehensive and sustainable development of society:

- Education;
- Culture;
- Sports;
- Health;
- Ecology.

That type of support can be reached through intellectual, financial, non-monetary donations, partnership support, volunteering, and other forms (such as blood donation, etc.). Thus, businesses can play a significant role in improving the prosperity of any society. So, CSR is a concept that lies at the core of the business management system.

Each company has a set of obligations to the state and society, which include paying taxes fully and on time, ensuring that employees are paid at least the minimum wage set by the government, and so on. This is the legal responsibility of the company. Whereas, CSR is a type of activity entirely based on the principle of voluntarism. That is why, there are various opinions about it. According to the classical approach, the sole purpose of businesses is profit maximization and thus, only the government should concern itself with the social well-being of its citizens. However, the second approach suggests that the main task of businesses is not only profit maximization but also social responsibility. According to this approach, CSR reduces short-term profits by engaging businesses in activities aimed at solving social problems. However, in the long run, it brings continuous benefits by creating a favorable social environment. In other words, addressing social problems improves people's prosperity, and vice versa, citizens with higher prosperity are more likely to bring benefits to the businesses. People trust the company that values humanity. When a company announces that it will allocate a certain portion of the income from the product to CSR projects and creates a suitable environment for that, it also brings positive impact to the company. In other words, a company that engages in activities aimed at solving social problems not only increases the purchasing power of customers but also maximizes its profit. Ensuring the personal participation of employees in the project also increases their work capacity and social responsibility. Thus, CSR benefits both the company and society. In addition to

all of this, CSR is also a philanthropic concept. Fulfilling a company's CSR means being responsible to all stakeholders (investors, customers, partners, employees, suppliers, etc.), being responsible to the environment, and considering these characteristics in all decisions. Its impact is determined by the company's economic, social, and environmental activities, as well as by its relations with various interested parties, including shareholders, employees, customers, business partners, governments, and communities. CSR is not simply philanthropy, tax payment, or PR (public relations); it is the activity that involves the implementation of various social programs both internally and externally within the company. Therefore, decisions in the field of CSR are made by all levels of corporate management: company owners, boards of directors, and managers. Any production and economic decisions are made considering their social and ecological consequences for both companies and society. CSR is turned into a strong factor in strategic development, business influence, and competitiveness. Since CSR is an investment that starts to yield results after a certain period, it should not be viewed by the company as an additional burden. It improves the company's impact on society and earns the trust of society. For these or other reasons, the implementation of CSR policies has already become an integral part of businesses.

While the proper implementation of CSR policy always leads to the development of society and the environment, different companies achieve this through various means, which include the protection of human and animal rights, health and safety, improving the level of education, environmental protection, enhancing working conditions, contributing to the state's economic development, and so on.

The evolution of the CSR concept can be divided into the following stages:

- Formation stage of the CSR concept (1950-1990)
- Development stage of the CSR concept (from 1990 to the present)

These stages differ from each other based on the main compatible concepts that reflect their nature, types, and methodologies.

The advantages that CSR brings to the company can be illustrated by the following examples:

- Customer satisfaction
- Employee satisfaction
- New business opportunities
- Opportunity to attract new skilled labor
- Reduction of expenses
- Improvement of public perception
- Improvement of financial indicators
- Increased capital liquidity

The success of the company is directly related to the health, stability and prosperity of the society. Companies participate in the life of local communities through the implementation of various social programs and actions. Examples of these include supporting the socially vulnerable population, providing material and moral support to children and young people, etc. Advanced foreign practices allow distinguishing the following main tools of social activity of business:

philanthropy, sponsorship, corporate volunteering and social marketing.

The results of the analyzes conducted by local and international consulting and independent funds show that the company's social activity will not be viewed as a business response to the expectations of the external environment. Social initiatives are the basis for building business reputation and positive image. In most cases, three social principles are considered in the implementation of social responsibility:

- Social responsibility based on its impact on the economy;
- Social responsibility based on its impact on society;
- Social responsibility based on its impact on the environment.

In advanced companies, social responsibility is carried out in several directions:

- Assistance in the development of science, education, and environmental protection;
- Support for projects aimed at the development and preservation of cultural heritage, contributing to national cultural development;
- Support for social development and public initiatives;
- Protection of health and welfare, including socially sensitive groups;
- Social responsibility based on its impact on the environment.

In order for these directions to be normal and to ensure business continuity, it is necessary that their activities meet the expectations of interested parties - the state, local authorities, staff, shareholders, investors and consumers. Socio-economic systems are also divided into two types:

- Self-regulating systems, which are based on customs, traditions, norms, ethics, and religious beliefs;
- Institutional, based on the conscious activity of management institutions in the application of economic, political, social, and technological tools.

These two governing influences mutually affect each other. Depending on the field of activity and economic power, the components of CSR concept may vary.

CSR can cover the following areas:

- Corporate social policy towards society;
- Corporate governance and corporate ethics;
- Protection of health and labor;
- Policy on environmental protection;
- Human rights;
- Human resource management;
- Mutual relations with communities, development, and investment attraction;
- Corporate philanthropy and volunteering;
- Meeting consumer demands and commitment to fair competition principles;
- Measures against bribery and corruption;
- Accountability, transparency, and information disclosure about activities;
- Compliance with human rights issues in relations with local and foreign suppliers, etc.

In international practice, CSR initiatives occupy a greater place in businesses' activities. Concluding the

above-mentioned literature findings, it can be suggested that the successful implementation of corporate social responsibility in the business sphere can lead business reputation increase of companies, growing capitalization, strengthening the unity of the labor team, developing transparency of the company for the public and increasing the investment attractiveness.

References

1. Carroll A. Corporate social responsibility: evolution of definitional construct. *Business and Society*, 1999. P 268-295.
2. Carroll A. The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of organizational Stakeholders/ *Business Horizons* 34(4) 1991. July-August. P. 39-48
3. "Green Marketing and Corporate Social Responsibility as its aspect" Ishpreet Kaur Yirdi, Assistant Professor, Mata Sundri College, Delhi University, Divya Gill, Gargi College, Delhi University Vol 7 Issue 8, 2016, pp.137-141.
4. "Corporate Social Responsibility & ITS DIFFERENT ASPECTS" Divya Gill Assistant Professor Kirori Mal College, Ishpreet Virdi Assistant Professor Mata Sundri College, Vol 5 Issue 5, 2014, pp.500-507.
5. Lantos, G.P., 2001. "The boundaries of strategic corporate social responsibility". *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(7), pp. 595-632.
6. Windsor, D., 2006. Corporate social responsibility: three key approaches. *Journal of Management Studies* 43(1), pp. 93-114
7. K. M. File and R. A. Prince. "Cause related marketing and corporate philanthropy in the privately held enterprise". *Journal of Business Ethics* 17, 1529-1539 (1998).
8. Humber, James M. (2002). «Beyond Stockholders and Stakeholders: A Plea for Corporate Moral Autonomy»: *Journal of Business Ethics*, 36 (3), pp. 215.
9. Carroll A. B. (2008), "A History of Corporate Social Responsibility: Concepts and Practices", In Crane A, McWilliams A, D. Matten, J. Moon and D. Siegel, the *Oxford Handbook of CSR*, Oxford University Press: Oxford., pp: 19-46.
10. Aguinis, H., and Glavas, A. (2012), "What we know and don't know about corporate social responsibility: A review and research agenda", *Journal of Management*, Vol: 38, No:6 pp: 932- 968.
11. Peloza, J., & Shang, J. (2011), "How can corporate social responsibility activities create value for stakeholders? A systematic review." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol: 39, pp: 117- 135.
12. Porter, M. E. and Kramer, M. R. (2006), "Strategy and Society: The link between Competitive Advantage and Corporate Social Responsibility." *Harvard Business Review*, Vol: 84, No:12, pp: 78-92.
13. Carroll A. Corporate social responsibility: evolution of definitional construct. *Business and Society*, 1999.P. 268-295.

14. Carroll A. The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders //Business Horizons 34(4) 1991. July-August. P. 39-48.
15. Social Investment Forum. <http://www.socialinvest.org>
16. The National council for public-private partnership // How PPPs work — <http://ncppp.org>
17. Cornuel E. Management Education and Corporate Global Responsibility. Global Responsibility № 2. The GRLI Partner Magazine. January, 2010. P. 13—16.
18. Johnson H. 2003. Does it pay to be good? Social responsibility and financial performance. Business Horizons 46 (6):34–40.
19. Schwartz M. S., Carroll A.B.2003. Corporate social responsibility: A three domain approach. Business Ethics Quarterly 13 (4):503–530.
20. Velasquez M. 2003. Debunking corporate moral responsibility. Business Ethics Quarterly 13 (4): 531–562.
21. Porter M. 2003. CSR-a religion with too many priests? European Business Forum(15). <http://www.eb-online.com>
22. Post J. E., Preston L. E., Sachs S. 2002. Redefining the Corporation: Stakeholder Management and Organizational Wealth. Stanford University Press: Stanford.
23. Oxford dictionary of Politics- <http://www.answers.com>
24. Report on socially investing trends in the United States, 2005. <http://www.socialinvest.org>
25. Singapore Government. Ministry of Finance / Public Private Partnership — <http://app.mof.gov.sg>
26. Slivinski S. The Corporate Welfare State How the Federal Government Subsidizes US Business //Policy Analysis, 2007. № 592 (May 14, 2007). P. 2—9.
27. Social Investment Forum. <http://www.socialinvest.org>
28. The National council for public-private partnership // How PPPs work — <http://ncppp.org>
29. U.S. Department of Transportation // www.fhwa.dot.gov